

IMPROVEMENT OF CITY TRANSPORTATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. This article The main quality indicators of city streets are: traffic safety, traffic convenience and traffic economy. These indicators shed light on the problems of visualizing the load level of the city street-road network, that is, the speed of movement in the form of the ratio of the road's carrying capacity.

Key words: speed of traffic, speed of movement, electronic brake, stabilization, hourly speed of movement, high mobility.

Today, the problems of urban public transport remain one of the most important in the complex development of cities and their operation at the level of demand. Problems such as the increase in city transport, the increase in the number of the city's population, and the congestion of the city's streets and roads have a significant impact on the traffic of passengers on bus routes in the city of Tashkent.

One of the most urgent problems today is the delay in the arrival time of passengers in city buses. Providing transport services to the flow of passengers, evaluating and predicting these processes is an important issue in the development of urban transport infrastructure.

In solving this issue, it is important to carry out targeted scientific research on providing transport services to the flow of passengers, their complete and selective inspection, and determining the critical parameters of the capacity of mode-changing facilities. At the same time, it is considered necessary to predict the parameters of the passenger flow in order to determine the probability of public passenger transport being caught, to make quick changes to its work schedule.

1. Transport comes from the Latin trans - "through" and portare - "to convey":

1. One of the most important branches of material production is passenger and cargo transportation [2];

2. Consolidation of all types of vehicles, technical devices and structures, communication routes, which ensure the process of transportation of people and cargo for various tasks from one place to another [3];

4. A set of technical systems designed to move people, goods and information from one place to another [4].

- Depending on the environment, the transport performing its tasks in a certain environment can be: atmospheric or aerial transport (planes, helicopters, balloons, airships, etc.);

- Surface transport, in particular, underground (metro and similar), rail (railway, tram and similar) and non-rail (car, motorcycle, bus, trolleybus) transport;

- Water transport (ship, boat, yacht and the like), including underwater (submarines) and space transport (missiles, satellites);

- Transport by service sector is divided into three categories: "Transport for general use serving the sphere of relations and population, transport for special (uncommon) use (transportation of raw materials, semi-finished products, finished goods, etc. within the production area) and transport for personal use" [5].

- Public transport should not be confused with public transport (public transport is a subcategory of public transport).

- Public transport serves trade and passenger transport.

Special transport is internal production and internal office transport.

- Finally, private transportation is private cars, motorcycles, mopeds, bicycles, yachts, airplanes, and the like.

Transportation is one of the main consumers of energy and one of the main sources of the greenhouse gas, carbon dioxide, which increases global warming. The reason for this is that internal combustion engines of land, air and water vehicles burn fossil fuels (mainly petroleum products - gasoline, kerosene and diesel fuel) in large

volumes. Approximately 1/4 of the carbon dioxide emissions released into the atmosphere due to the burning of energy fuels belong to the transport sector [6].

Examples of aspects of transportation that have a negative impact on the environment: air pollution with carbon dioxide gas and fine particulate matter, contamination of ground water with toxic runoff from highways and car washes and parking lots, noise emission, loss of urban living space (50% of the area of modern cities to roads, parking lots, garages, and gas stations) and the occupation of wild animals and agricultural land around the city. Urban passenger transport occupies a special place in the system of means of transport and connecting roads.

Urban public transport, including its modern rapid types, has not yet found the necessary development, if they had found their development, the acuteness of the problem of development of transport in megacities would have decreased significantly. In almost all sectors of the transport complex, the trend of obsolescence of fixed assets and their inefficient use remains. Depreciation of the main production funds for separate groups of fixed assets has reached 55-70% and this indicator continues to grow.

The condition of many technical means in the field of transport has reached a critical level. Most of them are being operated beyond the limit of normal service, that is, despite the fact that most of them have reached the end of their service life, and the rest are approaching this period.

As a result, safety indicators and economic efficiency of transport operation are significantly deteriorating.

The instability (imbalance) of the development of the unified transport system in the republic is one of the most important problems. This problem includes the three most important elements. The first of them is the disproportion in the pictures and scales of development of different types of transport.

The second is the existing transport, which is most acutely manifested in the fact that the level of development of highways does not correspond to the level of

automobilization and the demand and need for car transport, in the sharp reduction of the number of regional and local airports, as well as in the presence of a large number of "bottlenecks" at the junctions of certain types of transport. is explained by insufficient development of infrastructure.

The third problem is the uneven development of transport infrastructure across regions.

It is known that about 65-70 percent of total passengers in Tashkent use public passenger transport. For this reason, the organization of urban passenger transportation in accordance with the transport mobility of the population, their demand for transport, on the one hand, provides the need for public transport of the population, and on the other hand, it leads to further improvement of the economic performance of automobile companies.

At present, there are 9 bus depots and 3 unitary enterprises within "Toshshahartrankhizmat" JSC. Bus palaces operate 152 routes, carrying over 200 million passengers per year. 47.8% of them are passengers using monthly travel tickets and 2.2% are passengers with privileges.

1,000 buses are attached to these routes, 13,769 on Sundays and 17,860 on weekdays are planned, 52 of the vehicles used in them are large-capacity buses and 81 are small-capacity buses. The number of bus schedules is 112, the number of schedules for large-capacity buses is 519, and the number of schedules for small-capacity buses is 601. The average distance of the route network is 8678.9 km by road and 36.2 km by metro. Vehicles operate on the routes and provide transport service to passenger flows according to schedules 1228 on weekdays, 1112 on Saturdays and 1024 on Sundays. The communication speed of 29 vehicles under the management of "Toshshahartrankhizmat" JSC involved in the transportation of passenger flows is 24.34 km/h, and the speed of transportation is 21.46 km/h, that is, the difference between them is 2.88 km/h. Low communication and disposal speeds indicate that

public passenger transport traffic on the route and delays at intermediate stops are relatively large.

The total number of intermediate stations in the city of Tashkent is 2121, intermediate stations located in shopping centers - 727, intermediate stations in old structures - 365, glass intermediate stations - 211, intermediate stations without station structures - 452. The number of public passenger transport control rooms owned by JSC "Toshshahartranskhizmat" is 32, the number of route control rooms is 113, capital equipment control room building - 9, large mobile control room pavilion - 12, small mobile control room pavilion - 11 .

"Tashshahartranskhizmat" JSC managers regularly study the population's transport mobility and demand for public transport. Periodically, changes are made to the number of bus routes and timetables that are in high demand. For example, in the same year, 49-"TTZ - Dostlik metro", 63-"Korasuv 1-mavze - Yunusabad 9-daha", 83-"Yunusabad 6-dahasi - Excavator plant", 199-"Excavator plant" belonging to the 2nd bus palace - Institute of Physical Education", related changes were made to routes 8-"Sergeli 7-dahasi - Chilonzor 25-dahasi" belonging to the 4th bus palace.

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One of the most urgent problems today is the delay in the arrival time of passengers in city buses. Providing transport services to the flow of passengers, evaluating and predicting these processes is an important issue in the development of urban transport infrastructure. In solving this issue, it is important to carry out targeted scientific research on providing transport services to the flow of passengers, their complete and selective inspection, and determining the critical parameters of the capacity of mode-changing facilities.

At the same time, it is considered necessary to predict the parameters of the passenger flow in order to determine the probability of public passenger transport being caught, to make quick changes to its work schedule. [7].

When evaluating and predicting the processes of providing transport services to the flow of passengers in the city transport infrastructure, it is necessary to take into account many factors, such as studying the parameters of urban public transport, ensuring their mutual compatibility, and effectively organizing these processes.

Each of them requires a separate approach and a complex solution.

In order to ensure the implementation of these practical works, the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4230 of March 6, 2019 "ON MEASURES TO IMPROVE THE CARGO AND PASSENGER TRANSPORTATION SYSTEM" was adopted [1]. In accordance with the decision, it is necessary to evaluate the processes of providing transport services to the flow of passengers, to make appropriate adjustments to the traffic schedules of the city public transport, taking into account the changes in the parameters of the flow of passengers, and to ensure their mutual compatibility.

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